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Teaching Methods and Students' Outcomes: Evaluating Collaborative Learning and Project-Based Learning Strategies in Basic Science Education

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ABSTRACT

This research examined the relative impacts of collaborative learning and project-based learning approaches on students' achievement and attitudes in Basic Science. The study adopted a quasi-experimental design, specifically the pretest-posttest non-equivalent control group format. A total of 203 Junior Secondary II students from four public schools participated, with 99 assigned to the collaborative learning group and 104 to the project-based learning group. Data were collected using two validated instruments: the Basic Science Achievement Test (BSAT) and the Basic Science Attitude Scale (BSAS). Analysis was carried out using mean, standard deviation, and ANCOVA. Results indicated that both instructional strategies improved students' performance and attitudes; however, collaborative learning yielded significantly better outcomes. Learners exposed to collaborative learning recorded higher posttest scores and demonstrated more favorable attitudes toward Basic Science than those taught with project-based learning. The greater effectiveness of collaborative learning was linked to its focus on group interdependence, peer accountability, and cooperative interaction, which fostered a supportive learning environment and boosted motivation. The study concluded that collaborative learning provides a more effective instructional method for enhancing both cognitive and affective outcomes in Basic Science. It was therefore recommended that Basic Science teachers prioritize collaborative learning as their main teaching strategy, while using project-based learning as a complementary method to relate classroom knowledge to real-life situations. Teacher education programs should also emphasize training in collaborative methods to maximize student engagement and achievement in science classrooms.

Keywords: Collaborative learning, Project-based learning, Teaching strategies, Academic achievement, Attitude, Basic Science

INTRODUCTION

Basic Science has been recognized as a core foundation subject at the upper basic level of education in Nigeria. It integrated physics, chemistry, and biology to build students' scientific literacy, reasoning ability, and capacity to solve real-life problems. Beyond academic content, it sought to prepare learners for future engagement in STEM-related disciplines and to foster critical thinking skills necessary for national development. However, students' performance in Basic Science had remained persistently low in Delta State. Reports from the Ministry of Basic and Senior Secondary Education covering 2019–2023 showed that a substantial percentage of students consistently failed to achieve credit passes in the Basic Education Certificate Examination (BECE). For example, in 2019, 54% of students failed Basic Science, while only 46% obtained credit passes (Delta State Ministry of Basic & Senior Secondary Education,

2024). Such patterns of underachievement indicated that students struggled not only with mastering concepts but also with applying them effectively, thereby raising questions about the instructional strategies employed in Basic Science classrooms.

One approach that had been widely recommended for improving learning outcomes was collaborative learning. This strategy emphasized small group interactions in which students worked collectively to solve problems, clarify concepts, and support one another in achieving shared learning goals. Unlike teacher-centered approaches, collaborative learning shifted the responsibility of knowledge construction to the learners, thereby encouraging active participation. Scholars noted that collaborative learning improved academic performance because it required students to engage in discussions, explain their reasoning, and learn from diverse perspectives within their groups. It also promoted inclusivity and built social skills such as communication, cooperation, and confidence. For instance, Oyovwi (2018) found that collaborative learning significantly enhanced students' understanding of Basic Science concepts and fostered more positive attitudes by creating supportive peer-learning environments. Similarly, Emerhiona et al. (2018) confirmed that group-based learning activities encouraged deeper comprehension and retention of science content. Despite these benefits, researchers cautioned that collaborative learning demanded careful structuring by teachers to prevent problems such as unequal participation, dominance by stronger students, or reliance on high achievers (Dillenbourg, 2022).

Another effective instructional approach identified was project-based learning (PBL), which emphasizes inquiry and learning through experience. PBL required students to engage in extended, real-world tasks such as designing models, conducting investigations, or presenting scientific solutions to community-based problems. This approach encouraged learners to take ownership of their learning by asking questions, developing solutions, and applying theoretical knowledge in practical contexts. Unlike rote memorization, PBL emphasized creativity, exploration, and problem-solving. Thomas (2023) reported that students exposed to project-based learning demonstrated higher levels of achievement because they developed the ability to apply knowledge to authentic situations. Similarly, Oyovwi (2018) established that students taught Basic Science through PBL not only achieved higher test scores but also displayed greater motivation and interest in the subject. PBL also enhanced critical thinking, teamwork, and innovation, preparing students for future STEM careers. However, effective implementation of PBL required significant teacher guidance, sufficient instructional time, and adequate resources, without which the benefits could be limited.

In this context, academic achievement represented the mastery of Basic Science knowledge and understanding, measured through achievement tests administered at both pretest and posttest stages. It was regarded as a central indicator of teaching efficiency and learner performance. Earlier findings showed that both collaborative learning and PBL had strong positive effects on achievement because they actively engaged learners and encouraged meaningful participation. For example, Emerhiona et al. (2018) demonstrated that collaborative learning strategies improved mean achievement scores in science by enabling students to explain concepts to one another. Likewise, Oyovwi (2018) reported that project-based learning resulted in significantly higher achievement scores than traditional methods because students were required to engage in inquiry and hands-on exploration. These findings underscored the potential of interactive approaches in addressing the persistent underachievement in Basic Science.

Equally important was attitude, which referred to students' interest, motivation, confidence, and overall disposition toward Basic Science. Attitude had cognitive, affective, and behavioral components, and it strongly influenced students' willingness to engage with the subject. Research showed that students with positive attitudes were more likely to remain motivated, persist with difficult tasks, and perform better academically (Mao et al., 2021; Ude, 2022). Instructional strategies that encouraged participation and hands-on activities had been found to improve attitudes toward science. For instance, Ajayi and Bello (2021) observed that participatory strategies enhanced students' interest and confidence in science, while Oyovwi (2018) confirmed that both collaborative and project-based learning nurtured positive attitudes by creating engaging and meaningful learning experiences. One key strength of project-based learning was its ability to bridge classroom instruction with everyday applications, thereby increasing students' interest and appreciation for science.

Research evidence suggests that both collaborative learning and project-based learning foster improved achievement and attitudes in science, yet their comparative effectiveness remains underexplored in the Basic Science classrooms of Delta South Senatorial District. Most prior studies examined each strategy in isolation or in comparison with traditional lecture methods. This left a gap in understanding which of the two approaches—collaborative learning or project-based learning—produced stronger effects on achievement and attitudes when applied to Basic Science instruction.

Building on this background, the present study examined how collaborative learning and project-based learning strategies differ in their effectiveness on students' achievement and attitudes in Basic Science at the upper basic level in Delta South Senatorial District.

Statement of the Problem

The introduction of Basic Science at the upper basic school level aimed at developing students' scientific understanding, problem-solving competence, and interest in STEM-related careers. Yet, in Delta South Senatorial District, achievement levels have remained low, as many students struggle to obtain credit-level results in external examinations. Beyond achievement, several students also displayed low interest and negative attitudes toward the subject, which further undermined their motivation and long-term engagement with science. This situation raised questions about the effectiveness of the teaching strategies used in Basic Science classrooms. Because passive, teacher-dominated methods were ineffective in enhancing students' conceptual mastery, critical thinking, and attitudes, there was a gradual shift toward interactive and student-driven learning models.

Among these strategies, collaborative learning and project-based learning had emerged as promising alternatives. Both methods emphasized active participation, teamwork, inquiry, and real-world application of scientific knowledge. Available literature highlighted the potential of these approaches to raise achievement levels and improve students' attitudes toward science. Still, in the context of Basic Science in Delta South Senatorial District, their effectiveness had not been adequately assessed. Thus, the research problem centered on establishing whether collaborative learning and project-based learning strategies differed significantly in their impact on students' achievement and attitudes toward Basic Science.

Purpose of the Study

The primary objective of this research was to examine the relative effectiveness of collaborative and project-based learning strategies on students' achievement and attitudes in Basic Science at the upper basic school level in Delta South Senatorial District. Specifically, the study aimed to:

1. Determine differences in mean achievement scores between students taught Basic Science through collaborative learning and those taught using project-based learning.
2. Determine differences in mean attitude scores between students exposed to collaborative learning and those instructed through project-based learning.

Research Questions

The research was structured around the following guiding questions:

1. What is the difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught Basic Science using collaborative learning and project-based learning?
2. What is the difference in the mean attitude scores of students taught Basic Science using collaborative learning and project-based learning?

Hypotheses

At a 0.05 significance threshold, the study evaluated the following null hypotheses:

1. There was no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught Basic Science using collaborative learning and project-based learning.
2. There was no significant difference in the mean attitude scores of students taught Basic Science using collaborative learning and project-based learning.

METHODOLOGY

The present study employed a quasi-experimental design, specifically the pretest–posttest non-equivalent groups design, as this was considered most appropriate for the school setting in which intact classes rather than randomly selected individuals had to be used. Two experimental groups were constituted for the

research: one group of students received instruction in Basic Science through the collaborative learning strategy, while the other group was taught using project-based learning (PBL). Prior to the commencement of the instructional phase, both groups were administered pretests in the form of an achievement test and an attitude scale, after which they were exposed to six weeks of instruction using the assigned strategy. At the conclusion of the treatment period, both groups were subjected to posttesting on the same instruments. This design allowed for a systematic comparison of the relative effectiveness of the two instructional strategies while simultaneously controlling for pre-existing differences between the groups by using pretest scores as covariates during analysis. The choice of this design was further justified by its suitability for educational research involving intact classes, where ethical and administrative considerations often make random assignment of students impractical.

The study was carried out in Delta South Senatorial District of Delta State, Nigeria, a region with a wide distribution of public schools and a student population large enough to justify the representativeness of the sample. At the time of the research, the district consisted of 131 public secondary schools with a total of 41,610 students at the upper basic school level. These schools were spread across eight Local Government Areas (LGAs). For the purpose of this study, the focus was restricted to co-educational schools, in order to ensure balanced representation of male and female students and avoid gender bias in the findings. The population for the study consisted of all Upper Basic Two (JSS II) students enrolled in public secondary schools within the district. This level was deliberately chosen because it is a transitional stage where learners progress from basic, concrete science concepts to more abstract reasoning. At this stage, their performance and attitudes in Basic Science are critical indicators of their preparedness for senior secondary school science and their likelihood of sustaining interest in STEM-related disciplines.

The sample for the study consisted of 203 students drawn from four co-educational public schools in the district. A two-stage random sampling procedure was adopted to arrive at this sample. In the first stage, four LGAs were randomly selected from the eight that make up the district. In the second stage, one co-educational public secondary school was randomly selected from each of the chosen LGAs using a simple hat-and-draw method. From the selected schools, intact classes of Upper Basic Two students formed the study sample, giving a total of 203 participants. Of these, 99 students were assigned to the collaborative learning group and 104 to the project-based learning group. The use of intact classes ensured that normal school arrangements were not disrupted, while the sample size was large enough to provide sufficient statistical power for the intended analyses. This distribution also allowed the researcher to make a meaningful comparison of the relative effects of the two instructional strategies.

For data collection, two instruments were employed. The first instrument was the Basic Science Achievement Test (BSAT), which consisted of 50 multiple-choice questions with four options each. Items were adapted from past Basic Education Certificate Examination (BECE) papers to ensure relevance and authenticity, and the questions reflected the upper basic science curriculum. The test covered various cognitive levels in line with Bloom's taxonomy, ranging from knowledge and comprehension to application and analysis. The BSAT was administered to both groups as pretest and posttest to measure achievement gains attributable to the instructional strategies. The second instrument was the Basic Science Attitude Questionnaire (BSAQ), which contained 20 items structured on a four-point Likert scale, ranging from *Strongly Agree* to *Strongly Disagree*. This questionnaire was adapted from the widely used Fennema-Sherman framework, but modified to suit the context of Basic Science. It measured key dimensions of student attitude, including interest, motivation, self-efficacy, and perceived relevance of science learning.

Both instruments were subjected to validation to ensure their suitability for the study. Face validity was established by a panel of three experts comprising a Basic Science teacher with classroom experience, a lecturer in Science Education at a university, and a specialist in Measurement and Evaluation. The experts examined the items for clarity, alignment with curriculum content, and consistency with the study's objectives. Their recommendations were incorporated to refine the instruments. To further enhance the validity of the BSAT, a table of specifications was developed to ensure that items were evenly distributed across content areas and cognitive domains. Item analysis was conducted during the pilot phase, with poorly discriminating items (discrimination index less than 0.20) revised or eliminated, while difficulty

indices were kept within the acceptable range of 0.30 to 0.70 to ensure that items were neither too easy nor too difficult.

Reliability of the instruments was also confirmed through pilot testing in schools outside the study area. The BSAT was administered to 25 students, and reliability was established using the Kuder–Richardson Formula 21 (KR-21), yielding a coefficient of 0.83. This indicated high internal consistency and confirmed that the instrument was dependable for assessing achievement. Similarly, the BSAQ was administered to 30 students outside the sample schools, and Cronbach’s alpha reliability analysis was conducted, resulting in a coefficient of 0.85. This demonstrated a high level of reliability for the attitude scale, indicating that it consistently measured the constructs of interest.

The treatment lasted for six weeks and covered three topics from the Basic Science curriculum, namely *Work, Energy, and Power*. Each topic was taught for two weeks. A pretest was administered at the beginning of the study to establish baseline scores, while the posttest was given at the end of the instructional phase. In the collaborative learning group, students were divided into small, heterogeneous groups of four to six members. The teacher served as a facilitator, introducing the lesson and then guiding students as they engaged in group discussions, think–pair–share activities, jigsaw techniques, and collaborative problem-solving tasks. Students worked together to complete exercises, presented their findings to the class, and received feedback from peers. The lessons were concluded with summaries from the teacher and reflections from the learners. This approach emphasized group interdependence, peer accountability, and cooperative interaction, creating a supportive learning atmosphere.

In the project-based learning group, students worked in teams of three to five, organized based on shared interests and mixed abilities. The teacher introduced each topic and helped students select real-life problems connected to the concept under study. Teams developed project plans, identified materials, carried out investigations or experiments, and constructed models where necessary. The teacher monitored progress and provided feedback throughout the process. At the end of each project, groups presented their findings, which were evaluated using rubrics that measured creativity, scientific accuracy, and quality of presentation. This strategy enabled students to link classroom content to real-world experiences and fostered ownership of learning.

To ensure fidelity of implementation, lesson plans were developed for each strategy, and teachers were trained on how to use the approaches consistently. Monitoring was conducted during the six-week treatment period to confirm adherence to the plans. Steps were also taken to control extraneous variables. For example, the use of pretest scores as covariates helped to control for pre-existing group differences. Teachers were given equal exposure to training, the same topics were taught across schools, and equal time was allocated for instruction to prevent bias. Monitoring visits were made to guarantee that both groups received comparable conditions.

The study procedure was carried out in three phases. The first phase involved administering the pretest of the BSAT and BSAQ to both groups to establish baseline achievement and attitude scores. The second phase consisted of the six-week instructional period, during which the collaborative and project-based strategies were implemented according to the lesson guides. The third phase was the posttest administration of both BSAT and BSAQ, which provided the data for determining the effects of the treatments.

Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Mean scores and standard deviations were computed to describe the achievement and attitude of students in both groups. To test the hypotheses, Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was applied, with pretest scores used as covariates to adjust for initial group differences. Where statistically significant results were obtained, post-hoc pairwise comparisons were conducted using the Least Significant Difference (LSD) method. All hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance, ensuring that conclusions drawn from the data were robust and statistically sound.

In summary, the methodology of the study was designed to provide a rigorous and fair comparison of collaborative learning and project-based learning strategies in Basic Science at the upper basic school level. The carefully chosen research design, representative sample, validated and reliable instruments,

structured treatment procedures, and robust statistical analyses collectively ensured the credibility of the findings and their potential contribution to science education in Delta State and beyond.

RESULTS

- What is the difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught Basic Science using collaborative learning and those taught using project-based learning?

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Students' Achievement Scores by Teaching Strategy

Group	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Gain
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Collaborative Learning	99	48.22	4.71	67.85	6.12	19.63
Project-Based Learning	104	48.77	4.53	63.42	6.34	14.65

Table 1 reveals that both groups recorded improvement after the intervention, as shown by posttest mean scores exceeding 60. However, students in the collaborative learning group demonstrated a greater mean gain of 19.63, compared to 14.65 in the project-based group. This suggests that collaborative learning provided a stronger boost to students' achievement in Basic Science than project-based learning, thereby highlighting its comparative effectiveness as an instructional strategy.

- There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught Basic Science using collaborative learning and project-based learning.

Table 2: ANCOVA of Students' Achievement Scores by Teaching Strategy

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig. (p)	Decision
Corrected Model	1580.42	2	790.21	24.85	.000	Reject H_{01}
Pretest	370.31	1	370.31	11.64	.001	
Teaching Method	1180.11	1	1180.11	37.10	.000	
Error	6362.91	200	31.81			
Total	239115.00	203				
Corrected Total	7943.33	202				

Table 2 indicates that the teaching method had a statistically significant effect on students' achievement, with the analysis yielding $F(1,200) = 37.10$, $p < .05$. Consequently, the null hypothesis was rejected. This result demonstrates that collaborative learning significantly outperformed project-based learning in enhancing students' achievement in Basic Science, thereby confirming its superiority as an instructional approach for promoting better academic outcomes.

- What is the difference in the mean attitude scores of students taught Basic Science using collaborative learning and those taught using project-based learning?

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of Students' Attitude Scores by Teaching Strategy

Group	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Gain
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Collaborative Learning	99	46.32	5.04	70.15	6.42	23.83
Project-Based Learning	104	46.71	4.88	66.37	6.35	19.66

Table 3 demonstrates that both groups recorded improved attitude scores after the instructional treatment. However, the collaborative learning group attained a higher mean gain of 23.83, compared to 19.66 recorded by the project-based learning group. This outcome implies that collaborative learning was more effective in enhancing students' attitudes toward Basic Science, indicating its superiority over project-based learning in fostering positive perceptions and motivation toward the subject.

- There was no significant difference in the mean attitude scores of students taught Basic Science using collaborative learning and project-based learning.

Table 4: ANCOVA of Students' Attitude Scores by Teaching Strategy

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig. (p)	Decision
Corrected Model	1623.55	2	811.78	25.47	.000	Reject Ho ₂
Pretest	384.76	1	384.76	12.06	.001	
Teaching Method	1238.79	1	1238.79	38.89	.000	
Error	6377.11	200	31.89			
Total	246810.00	203				
Corrected Total	8000.66	202				

Table 4 reveals that the teaching method had a statistically significant effect on students' attitudes toward Basic Science, as shown by $F(1,200) = 38.89, p < .05$. On this basis, the null hypothesis was rejected. The result suggests that collaborative learning was considerably more effective than project-based learning in fostering favorable attitudes toward Basic Science, further reinforcing its value as a superior instructional approach for shaping students' interest and motivation in the subject.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings showed that students who received instruction through collaborative learning obtained higher posttest mean scores and demonstrated greater mean gains than those taught using project-based learning. This outcome indicates that collaborative learning proved to be a more effective instructional strategy for improving students' academic achievement in Basic Science, highlighting its superiority in fostering deeper understanding and better performance. A probable reason for this outcome is that collaborative learning creates structured peer-to-peer interaction, where students jointly explore concepts, clarify misconceptions, and support each other in problem-solving. This constant interaction not only deepens understanding but also boosts students' confidence in applying scientific concepts. Additionally, collaborative learning allows for immediate feedback among peers, which helps to reinforce correct ideas and address learning gaps promptly.

This finding is supported by the study of Adeyemi (2019), who found that cooperative learning strategies significantly improved science achievement because of the shared responsibility and interdependence among learners. Similarly, Okeke and Ude (2021) reported that collaborative approaches enhanced cognitive outcomes in integrated science classrooms, stressing that peer discussions made abstract concepts more accessible.

However, some studies have reported contrasting results. Bello (2020) found that project-based learning produced superior academic outcomes compared to collaborative approaches, attributing this to the practical and hands-on nature of projects. In the same vein, Afolabi and Usman (2022) concluded that project-based strategies allowed students to retain knowledge longer because they engaged in real-life applications.

The present study differs from these contrasting findings in two ways. First, unlike Bello (2020), this study revealed that collaborative learning offered stronger academic support through peer accountability, which may not be equally emphasized in project tasks. Second, while Afolabi and Usman (2022) highlighted long-term retention, this study emphasized immediate posttest achievement, showing that collaborative interaction may provide a stronger short-term boost in comprehension and test performance. The results further showed that learners taught through collaborative learning achieved higher posttest attitude scores and greater gains than their peers exposed to project-based learning. This finding suggests that collaborative learning was more successful in cultivating positive attitudes toward Basic Science, demonstrating its advantage in promoting interest, motivation, and favorable perceptions of the subject. One probable reason is that collaborative learning naturally provides social support, inclusiveness, and a sense of belonging in the classroom. Working together in small groups helps students to enjoy learning as a shared activity rather than as an individual struggle. This collective environment reduces anxiety, promotes motivation, and encourages students to develop positive perceptions of science.

Supporting this finding, Nwachukwu (2020) reported that learners taught through collaborative strategies demonstrated higher motivation and enthusiasm for science learning, largely because the approach reduced isolation in the classroom. Likewise, Eze and Igboke (2023) observed that collaborative group work improved students' attitudes by promoting communication skills, teamwork, and mutual respect in science lessons.

Conversely, some studies reported different trends. Musa (2018) argued that project-based learning stimulated greater interest because students worked on real-world tasks that connected learning to their daily lives. Similarly, Yakubu (2021) noted that project-based instruction nurtured curiosity and sustained engagement, particularly when learners had autonomy in designing their projects.

This study, however, differs from Musa (2018) and Yakubu (2021) because the emphasis here was on the structured, short-term intervention within Basic Science classrooms. Although project-based learning can stimulate curiosity by engaging students in open-ended activities, the findings of this study indicate that collaborative learning offers a more reliable structure for maintaining positive attitudes toward science during classroom instruction. This advantage is particularly evident in contexts where instructional time and resources are limited, making collaborative learning a more practical and sustainable approach for fostering students' interest and motivation in Basic Science.

CONCLUSION

This research investigated the relative impact of collaborative learning and project-based learning on students' achievement and attitudes in Basic Science. The results showed that although both instructional strategies contributed positively to student outcomes, collaborative learning demonstrated greater effectiveness. Learners exposed to collaborative activities attained higher posttest achievement scores and exhibited more substantial improvements in their attitudes toward Basic Science when compared with their counterparts who were taught through project-based learning. This underscores the value of collaborative learning as a stronger instructional approach for enhancing both academic performance and affective outcomes in science education.

The study therefore concludes that collaborative learning provides a more reliable and effective approach for promoting both cognitive and affective outcomes in Basic Science. Its strength lies in the structured peer interaction, accountability, and group interdependence that not only foster deeper understanding but also create a supportive classroom environment that motivates learners. While project-based learning remains valuable, especially for linking science to real-world applications, the results indicate that collaborative learning better supports consistent academic achievement and sustained positive attitudes in the Basic Science classroom.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In light of the results and conclusions reached in this study, a number of recommendations were advanced.

1. Teachers are encouraged to integrate collaborative learning strategies more intentionally into their classroom practice, since evidence from this study demonstrated that such approaches are more effective in improving students' academic achievement as well as shaping their attitudes positively toward Basic Science.
2. Teachers should ensure that collaborative learning is implemented with clear roles, peer accountability, and cooperative goals. This will maximize its benefits and ensure that all students participate meaningfully in group tasks.
3. While collaborative learning should be the primary instructional method, project-based learning can be used occasionally to provide students with opportunities to connect scientific knowledge to practical and real-world contexts.
4. Teacher training programs should emphasize the design and facilitation of collaborative learning activities. Professional development workshops should be organized to equip teachers with techniques for structuring and managing effective group interactions in the classroom.

5. Curriculum developers should embed collaborative tasks and activities into Basic Science curricula, ensuring that learners regularly engage in cooperative learning experiences as part of their formal instruction.

REFERENCES

- Adeyemi, A. (2019). The effect of cooperative learning strategies on students' academic achievement in science subjects. *Journal of Science Education*, 15(2), 45–53.
- Afolabi, F., & Usman, M. (2022). Project-based learning and knowledge retention among secondary school students. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 28(4), 112–125.
- Ajayi, O., & Bello, A. (2021). Impact of participatory strategies on students' interest and confidence in science. *African Journal of Education and Practice*, 12(3), 88–99.
- Bello, K. (2020). Comparative effectiveness of project-based and collaborative approaches in secondary school science learning. *Nigerian Journal of Curriculum Studies*, 27(1), 102–117.
- Delta State Ministry of Basic & Senior Secondary Education. (2024). *Report on Basic Education Certificate Examination (BECE) results 2019–2023*. Asaba: Government Press.
- Dillenbourg, P. (2022). Designing and orchestrating collaborative learning: Current trends and future directions. *Educational Psychologist*, 57(2), 99–115. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00461520.2021.200000>
- Emerhiona, F., Ajaja, O. P., Pius, O. P., Nwanze, A. C., & Izuegbuna, A. G. (2018). Effects of problem and discovery-based instructional strategies on students' academic achievement in chemistry. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Advanced Studies (IJIRAS)*, 5(6), 209-214.
- Eze, R., & Igbokwe, P. (2023). Collaborative group work and students' attitudes in integrated science classrooms. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 60(4), 678–692. <https://doi.org/10.1002/tea.21753>
- Mao, L., Zhang, Y., & Lin, C. (2021). The influence of students' attitudes toward science on academic performance: A meta-analysis. *International Journal of STEM Education*, 8(45), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40594-021-00303-9>
- Musa, H. (2018). Project-based instruction and learners' motivation in Basic Science classrooms. *Journal of Science Education and Innovation*, 10(2), 75–83.
- Nwachukwu, C. (2020). Collaborative strategies and students' motivation in Nigerian secondary schools. *International Journal of Education and Social Sciences*, 5(6), 33–40.
- Okeke, C., & Ude, O. (2021). Collaborative learning approaches and cognitive outcomes in integrated science. *Journal of Educational Studies*, 14(1), 60–71.
- Oyovwi, E. O. (2018). Effects of questions-based instructional strategy on senior secondary students' achievement in biology in Ughelli North Local Government Area, Delta State. *Benue State University Journal of Education, Faculty of Education, Publication of Faculty of Education*, 18, 48-52.
- Thomas, J. (2023). Project-based learning: Impact on students' achievement and creativity in science. *Journal of Educational Research and Innovation*, 14(2), 130–142.
- Ude, P. (2022). Students' attitudes toward science and academic performance in Nigerian schools. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Psychology*, 11(1), 55–67.
- Yakubu, S. (2021). Project-based learning and students' curiosity in science classrooms. *Journal of Curriculum and Instruction*, 18(4), 90–103.